

1 **Fatty acid signaling is activated during trophectoderm lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here activation of fatty
8 acid signaling during lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo. This
9 included changes in FA2H, FFAR4 and FADS2.

10 Citations

11 1. Alderson, N.L., Rembiesa, B.M., Walla, M.D., Bielawska, A., Bielawski, J. and Hama, H., 2004.
12 The human FA2H gene encodes a fatty acid 2-hydroxylase. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 279(47),
13 pp.48562-48568.

14 2. Wang, W., Li, J., Cui, S., Li, J., Ye, X., Wang, Z., Zhang, T., Jiang, X., Kong, Y., Chen, X. and
15 Chen, Y.Q., 2024. Microglial Ffar4 deficiency promotes cognitive impairment in the context of metabolic
16 syndrome. *Science Advances*, 10(5), p.eadj7813.